

A Study on Brand Resonance of Yamaha at AMS Motors Puducherry

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ABSTRACT

Brand resonance is an important concept for marketers to develop a long-term relationship with consumers through their brand and brand loyalty, brand attachment, brand community and brand engagement are the four factors which strongly builds brand resonance. The object of the study is to find the most influencing factors of brand resonance for Yamaha and to find the significant association between brand resonance and income level of the consumers and to find the significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the consumers. This study has a total population of 100 and the sample size is 80, and it used simple random sampling. Through questionnaire, primary data was collected and by referring books, journals and company records, secondary data was collected. This study used various statistical tools like chi-square test and ANOVA to arrive a meaningful conclusion. This study is conclude that, there is no significant association between brand resonance and income level of the respondents and there is no significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the respondents and the most influencing factor of brand resonance is brand community.

KEYWORDS: Brand resonance, brand loyalty, brand attachment, brand community, brand engagement, Yamaha

INTRODUCTION

According to Keller brand resonance refers to the nature of the relationship that customers have with the brand and the extent to which they feel that they are “in synch” with the brands. With the consideration of the definition of brand resonance which was coined by Keller brand resonance is the nature of relationship and level of identification the customer has with the brand. Brand resonance can be defined as how well you connect with your customer both formally and casually. Creating resonance with your brand means your message has to permeate consumers’ minds and lives” (Stratfold, 2012). Brand resonance is the extent to which a consumer develops strong behavioural, psychological, and social bonds with the brands s/he consumes (Rindfleisch et al., 2005). Brand Resonance refers to the nature of the relationship that the consumer has with the brand (Bourbab & Boukill, 2008).

Brand resonance can be divided into four categories; these categories based on the strength of customer relationship that they has with brand.

Brand Loyalty

Loyalty is the initial stage of brand resonance formation, it characterized by repeat purchase and amount of category volume attributed to the brand. Here we can analyse how frequently consumers buy a brand and what quality they purchased. We can measure brand loyalty in terms of re-buy.

Brand Attachment

In the stage of attachment customer buy out of necessity but it is depends if brand is the only product easily available and this product one they can afford. For the creation of resonance the customer preferred brand must have something unique in border context.

Brand Community

Keller define this stage as ‘sense of community’ this stage characterized by attachment of consumer with brand through brand community. Consumer’s identity himself with brand community is a reflected as an important social phenomenon, through which consumer feels an affiliation with other people that are associated with brand.

Brand Engagement

This stage occur when consumers ready to invest time, energy, money or other resource into the brand, beyond those expended during purchase and consumption. Customers themselves become brand evangelists and help to communicate about the brand and strengthen the brand ties of other.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Raut, U. R. revealed that the existing, as well as new conceptual models of brand resonance, represented a good fit with the data. Between the two model contexts, the model in which we add two mediators of brand resonance such as

How to cite this paper: Ruth. H | Nirmala. G "A Study on Brand Resonance of Yamaha at AMS Motors Puducherry"

Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.451-454, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29127.pdf>

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brand satisfaction and brand trust shows quite a good fit with the data as compared to existing model of brand resonance.

Kumar, Y., & Jayabharathi, S. revealed that the brand resonance is the relationship between consumer(s) and their brand(s). Based on above construct of brand resonance it reveals that brand resonance and brand, relationship is merely same concept and with the consideration of above construct. We can use brand resonance instead of brand relationship in the branding research. The literature of branding does not explain the impact and relationship of demographic characteristics of consumers with brand relationship. It is to be found out how the demographics characteristics of consumers help to building a brand relationship.

Jori van den bosch & venetis revealed that the research contributes to current literate on Customer-based brand equity and provides a base for the development of metrics wherein both behavioral- and affective dimensions are integrated. Brand resonance seems to be better in explaining the actual behavior (Share-of-wallet) of consumers, than a stated preference, which is a big step forward in the development of brand performance indicators. Furthermore, this metric can facilitate a better measurement of the strength of different marketing activities as well as the valuation of the magnitude those activities have on a brand.

Varjonen, I. revealed that the behavioural loyalty can be built through SENSE, FEEL and RELATE experiences. Attitudinal attachment with SENSE, FEEL, THINK and RELATE experiences, sense of community with THINK, ACT and RELATE experiences and active engagement with THINK and RELATE experiences. The overall brand resonance can be built through SENSE, FEEL, THINK and RELATE experiences.

Aurchi, M. R. revealed that Bangladesh is a regenerative country, which is growing, making its presence in the global forum. Moreover it is one of the countries that are looked upon as the next growth centre. So let us be conscious about the fact that there is a regenerative Bangladesh, creative Bangladesh, path breaking Bangladesh. Hopefully Business process outsourcing is the next opportunity for Bangladesh. Enroute international limited is doing tremendously well in BPO sector in Bangladesh. Though is a newly established organization, working for only 6 years but it has a depth of

resources especially who is leading the organization. So if they want to achieve the goal, they need to ensure the proper learning for the each and every employee. I hope enrouté's skilled and efficient employees will make sure all success for the organization for the long run.

Burgess, J., & Spinks, W. revealed that the examination of the literature on the four factors of brand resonance based on Keller's theory (2009). Each factor generates positive worth for brands such as increased purchases and repurchases, stronger loyalty to products and brands, positive word of mouth, affective commitment towards the brand and profitability. Therefore when a consumer is exhibiting all four factors, they will generate greater worth. Despite the lack of attention of Keller's brand resonance theory in the literature, this literature review indicates that the theory is of value and merits further use and research. This is further supported by the theoretical application of the factors of brand resonance to video games, a growth industry which warrants further analysis and empirical testing.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out the most influencing factor of brand resonance for Yamaha products at AMS Motors.
2. To find the significant association between brand resonance and income level of the consumers.
3. To find the significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the consumers.

HYPOTHESIS

1. H₀: There is no significant association between brand resonance and income level of the consumers.
2. H₀: There is no significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the consumers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research used for the study was descriptive and it was based on the both primary data and secondary data. In Primary data, the data were collected through questionnaire from the customers of AMS Motors and the secondary data was collected from the books, journals, websites and company records. This study has a total population of 100 and the sample size for the study was 80. The type of sampling used in the study was simple random sampling. Statistical tools like chi-square test and ANOVA are used to arrive a meaningful conclusion.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table1 Showing frequency distribution of consumer profile

S. No	Consumer Profile		Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	52	65
		Female	28	35
		Total	80	100
2	Age	Below 25	28	35
		25-35	32	40
		35-45	15	19
		Above 45	5	6
		Total	80	100
3	Income	Below 20,000	38	48
		20,000-50,000	35	44
		51,000-1,00,000	6	7
		Above 1,00,000	80	1
		Total	80	100

4	Occupation	Private employee	32	40
		Government employee	30	37
		Businessman	15	19
		Student	3	4
		Total	80	100

SOURCE: Primary Data

INFERENCE:

The above table shows that the respondents covered for the study consist of 65% male respondents and 35% female respondents. The study reveals that 40% of respondents are in the age group of 25-35 years, 35% of respondents are below 25 years, 19% of respondents are in 35-45 years and only 6% of them are above 45. The income earned by 48% of the respondents was below Rs.20,000 monthly, 44% of respondents are getting Rs.21,000-50,000, 7% of respondents are getting Rs.51,000-1,00,000 and only 1% of the respondents are getting above Rs.1,00,000. 40% of the respondents are working in private concern, 37% of the respondents are government employees, 19% of the respondents are doing business and only 4% of the respondents are students.

Table2 Showing factors influencing Brand Resonance

S. NO	Factors	Maximum Score	Actual Score
1	Brand loyalty	2000	1453
2	Brand attachment	2000	1286
3	Brand community	2000	1511
4	Brand engagement	2000	1487

SOURCE: Primary Data

INFERENCE:

From the above table it was found that the most influencing factor of brand resonance is brand community for Yamaha at AMS Motors dealers.

Table3 Showing analysis using chi-square test

Attributes Brand Resonance	Income level of the customers			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	11	10	1	22
Moderate	3	3	0	6
High	24	28	0	2
Total	38	41	1	80

SOURCE: Primary Data

INFERENCE:

From the above table chi square value is 2.907 and P-value is 0.57 which is greater than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It is found that there is no significant association between brand resonance and income level of the consumers.

Table4 Showing analysis using ANOVA

Sources of Variance	SS	df	MS	F	P value
Between Groups	38641	4	9660.25	2.03496	0.14089
Within Groups	71207	15	4747.13		
Total	109848	19			

SOURCE: Primary Data

INFERENCE:

The above table shows that f value is 2.03 and p value is 0.14, since p value is greater than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It is found that there is no significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the consumers.

FINDINGS

The most influencing factor of brand resonance at AMS Motors dealers in Yamaha is brand community. By using chi-square test, it was found that P-value is 0.57 which is greater than 0.05 hence there is no significant association between brand resonance and income level of the consumers. By using ANOVA, it was found that P-value is 0.14 which is

greater than 0.05 hence there is no significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the consumers.

The study reveals that Yamaha products are trustable and the information given about the product is honest and reliable. 44% of the respondents strongly agree that quality of the product is satisfactory and 31% of the respondents agree that timely service and proper guidance relating to maintenance of the bike is given by the sales person. 38% of the respondents agree that the product establishes a unique image and consumer feel proud and magnificent. The Yamaha brand gives positive feelings towards the product and memorable value in the market.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The prime objective of the Yamaha Company is building long lasting relationship with customers; it is suggested not only in building relationship but also to maintain long lasting brand relationship between customers and brand.
2. The customer show less attachment with the brand, the company should pay extra attention towards the customers.
3. The company has to consider brand satisfaction and brand trust, as brand relationship booster elements, to improve the customer relationship with brand.
4. Some customers are not satisfied by the price of the product but they are influenced by the quality, so if the company can rework on the price without affecting the quality can attract more customer.

CONCLUSION

According to Keller, Brand resonance refers to the nature of the relationship that customers have with the brand and the extent to which they feel that they are “in synch” with the brands. The study conclude that by using chi square test there is no significant association between brand resonance and income level of the respondents and by using ANOVA it was concluded that there is no significant difference between brand resonance and age wise classification of the respondents and the most influencing factor of brand resonance at AMS Motors dealers in Yamaha is brand community.

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